

PROBLEMS CONTENTED IN NEWS AND INFORMATION PROGRAMS ON "KARAKALPAKSTAN" AND "YOUTH" TV CHANNELS

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Abstract: In the article, the content of informational courses, problems in courses, format and chronology of materials are given. In the course of the study, the diversity of the information programs broadcasted on the national TV channels was analyzed. Finally, it was revealed that there is a demand for an information system prepared in which genre of the joint audience. In the media market, the position of television sets as a commodity has been completely overtaken.

Key words: Television, television network, info show, content analysis, human resources

Television show is term for all programs broadcast on television. Television programs are broadcast on television channels. Each concert has its own set time, it is divided into genres, it is prepared and given to the air. It is important to fill the air with original and non-repetitive materials. Today, new demands are placed on informational programs. From a scientific theoretical point of view, the use of new methods in information processing is one of the actual issues. It doesn't do any harm to try the practical, researched, scientific aspect. Every detail is very important in the information program on television. The audience's attention would have been raised by the news that was given in a very sharp manner, and the news that was given in the form of news and information could be received by few readers. For example, it is possible to use a number of elements to keep the viewer's attention. For example: a news report with a frame change every four seconds helps to distance the audience from the raw material, but we do not use this theory in all materials. I don't like people who express a different opinion from me. "Move to reach the frame itself." However, beware of sharp meaning in the present. Such scenes divert the viewer's attention from the idea. Scientist says that this is "personnel inhumanity".

In the next paragraph, we will learn about the info sets, content, and content chronology of our TV channels.

"News" information program of "Karakalpakstan" TV channel

The TV channel's main informational program was also broadcasted on the "Week" informational show . On show day, one episode in Karakalpak language, one episode in Russian, and one episode in Uzbek language were broadcasted. It will be broadcast in the Karakalpak language at 20:00. The average broadcast time is 30 minutes, and the average number of materials is given in intervals of five materials. Of course is very little. Let's talk about the chronology of program content. On 18.06.2022, in the course of twenty-four minutes, a total of six materials were given, of which two news, one reportage, and three reports were given. Looking at the chronological order, Hamida Sultamuratova's report on the content of "Amendments to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was aired in the

KSU, and two interviews were conducted with the staff. The message input has been disabled. The following report was prepared in accordance with the meeting devoted to "Constitutional reform proposals, as well as today's ecological challenges" held at NSPI. The message included an interview and a video clip. The following material was prepared in the genre of reportage and consisted of an interview. H. Sultamuratova started with the introduction of the style, gave detailed information about the object, and started a little later about the works that were performed in the object. Additional conversational elements were also used, meaningful questions were asked in the interview. The content of the next plot genre has been prepared by the Ministry of Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan, responsible for finding suitable places to visit. In that case, it was noted that there were three objects, the implementation of sanitary and hygienic requirements, the conditions for children with disabilities, and the creation of necessary conditions for parents with children.

An interview was prepared from the Berdak Museum of Karakalpak Literature and Culture, and the use of various elements was used. The material was used from two interviews, graphics, video plots for a duration of 6 minutes.

Genre structure of "News" informational series

Genre is a genre format	Number of materials (10 on the air)
Informational message	19
Newness	8
Account	18
Interview	124
Report	12
Video plot (elements of video plot)	24
Advertising	2
Mobile interview	5
Mobile reportage	1

From them: Message: the whole thing is short. The materials in the report genre are prepared based on the implementation of the presidential decisions. Interviewer: information, information - analytical. Interviews: informative, analytical, portrait interviews. Reportages: thematic, special, and entertaining types were used.

Categories of given interviews %

Interviews with experts	Interviews with participants
57	43

We watched and learned three types of interviews on the "Karakalpakstan" TV channel in the materials given in this genre: informational, informational-analytical, portrait interviews.

Interview typology (% used in 10 materials)

Information	Information-analytic	Portrait
40,4	9,4	38,5

Most of the reports published in "News" information channel were given in the position of additional information in the introduction section of the report and other

materials. We would like to present the information we found in this regard. Message: In the reports prepared by Hamiyda Sultanmuratova, we saw the use of such types as stand-up, video story: presentation, archival materials. For example, the questions in the first interviews should be asked on the topic of the material, and the respondent should be encouraged to work according to the topic. In order to this, info-analytical interviews, video plots were used.

"Youth" TV channel "New Davr" news channel

We can say that the TV channel is very experienced, because the broadcast network is full of programs 24 hours a day. Through the "Period" information network, we publish reports and TV series about the achievements of talented people in sports, culture, science, literature, entertainment and other fields. Since then, in May 2017, MTRK's private TV channel, this channel, has been closed, and "New Period" informational channel has started to broadcast in its place. Recently, the TV channel launched the official online TV channel www.limehd.tv. It's the last social network with my own channel in the blocks. Here are the programs broadcast live. Over the years, the name of this organization has changed twice. The new era changed to "New Davr" at the time called "Davr". At the same time, the format, design, and content have really changed. Tuesday, March 2 from 19:00 to 19:40 and from 14:00 to 14:15. Repeat: 09:00 to 09:40. Another TV channel has "New Davr news" channel. The daily news of the TV channel is 2 hours and 10 minutes. In the meantime, the world is giving news about what is happening in our country.

Genre structure of "New Davr" chorus of "Youth" TV channel

Genre is a genre format	Number of materials (10 on the air)
Informational message	57
Newness	22
Account	13
Report	13
Interview	153
Video plot	66
Mobile reportage	2
Mobile interview	1
Advertising	0
Total	104 materials were given

If we analyze the serialization of the show, the continuity is the same as that of the "News" program, but the amount of information provided does not build the structure. We could see the difference in genre. The interviewer was brief and clear, and the materials prepared by the informants started with a direct connection to the object, and the part of the writing was almost shown. There were no slangs in the material texts, no spelling errors in the messages. From the given 104 materials, we learned that the text of the etude genre, which is left, is 2 times more beautiful. It is proved that there is a system for controlling the audience, and that it is an experience of the TV channel. It is worth mentioning one of the biggest news of the TV channel. Starting from 2023, the "New Davr" informational series began to be broadcast in the form of "live broadcast". The host of this news took the first place

in the rating of Uzbekistan TV channels. Instead of information, the number of informational shows broadcasted live by our republic has increased.

In addition, it was learned that the language, airtime, design, and schedule of informational programs on "Karakalpakstan" and "Youth" TV channels have changed. However, there was no noticeable difference in the format.

References:

1. <https://www.wikipedia.org>
2. Eric Fichtelius book "Fundamentals of Radio and Television Journalism, 10 Rules of Journalism", "West" Publishing House, Tashkent 2002. Page 60
3. Y. Pakhratdinov, A. Abdimuratov "Oratorical skills" (reading manual) Nukus "Karakalpakstan" 2020
4. Sh. Usnatdinov "Introduction to Journalism" (Reading manual) Nukus "Karakalpakstan" 2009
5. National University of Uzbekistan and Mirzo Ulugbeka "Dictionary: JOURNALISM, ADVERTISING, PUBLIC RELEASE" "Zar kalam" T., 2003
6. "Russian language|Russian" Ganieva E. R. Novye stranitsy istorii televydeniya Uzbekistana // Young learners. — 2017. — №21. — S. 57-59[[Category: articles with non-English text "
7. Ganiyeva, M. (2021). Effective Methods of TRIZ.
8. Ganiyeva, M. (2023). THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPING THE LOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS (IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS). Science and innovation, 2(B3), 30-33.
9. Ganieva, M. (2023, June). EMPOWERING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TIPS TECHNOLOGY. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 62-63).
10. Maftuna, G. (2021). Effective ways to Use Triz (The Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) in Elementary School. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 9, 85-88.

